

SAFERS: Structured Approaches for Forest fire Emergencies in Resilient Societies

Edoardo Arnaudo^{1,2}, Luca Bruno¹, Federico Oldani¹, Marko Laine³, Conrad Bielski⁴, Alberto Croci⁵, Andrea Trucchia⁶, Panagiota Masa⁷, and Claudio Rossi¹

¹ AI, Data & Space, LINKS Foundation, Italy, name.surname@linksfoundation.com

² DAUIN, Politecnico di Torino, Italy, name.surname@polito.it

³ Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI), Finland, name.surname@fmi.fi

⁴ Riscognition GmbH, Germany, name.surname@riscognition.com

⁵ WaterView s.r.l., Italy, name.surname@waterview.it

⁶ CIMA Foundation, Italy, name.surname@cimafoundation.org

⁷ Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH), Greece, gmasa@iti.gr

Abstract Forest fires, exacerbated by the increasing frequency and intensity of extreme weather events, remain a pressing concern. Developing effective forest fire emergency management systems is paramount to mitigate the impacts of future events. The SAFERS project (Structured Approaches for Forest fire Emergencies in Resilient Societies) addresses this challenge by proposing a modular and comprehensive Emergency Management System (EMS) encompassing all phases of the emergency management cycle. The main backbone of SAFERS is composed of Intelligent Services (ISs) linked with a web-based platform allowing data visualisation and end-user interactions. These services integrate diverse data sources, including Earth Observation data, meteorological forecasts, and crowdsourced information. Through advanced technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms, the ISs enable early warnings, rapid fire detection, propagation prediction, post-event assessment, and monitoring of soil recovery. This work focuses on these services and on the methodologies applied within SAFERS to enhance decision-making capabilities, facilitate effective response strategies, and promote resilience in the face of forest fire emergencies.

Keywords wildfires, earth observation, artificial intelligence, climate change

Introduction

Forest fires have become an escalating concern due to the intensifying frequency and severity of extreme weather conditions, exacerbated by the effects of climate change. This global issue not only results in the loss of human lives and habitats but also contributes to the release of millions of tons of CO² and other pollutants [1]. The development of effective forest fire emergency management systems becomes therefore crucial in minimising the impacts of future fire events.

The SAFERS project (Structured Approaches for Forest fire Emergencies in Resilient Societies) addresses this pressing challenge by proposing a comprehensive Emergency Management System (EMS) designed to manage forest fires across all critical phases of the emergency management cycle. Leveraging a service-oriented approach, SAFERS integrates a set of Intelligent Services (ISs), independent modules exploiting Artificial Intelligence (AI) and other advanced capabilities to provide more refined and informative outputs. These services utilise and produce diverse data sources, including Earth Observation from the EU Copernicus program, meteorological forecasts, hazards and risk forecasts, propagation models, data from social media and chatbot applications, as well as real-time data from in-situ camera sensors. The outputs generated by the SAFERS IS are stored within a geospatial data lake, harmonised, and made accessible to end users through an interactive web-based dashboard. This integration enables informed decision-making throughout the entire emergency management cycle, enhancing preparedness, response, and recovery efforts.

Compared to other solutions, the SAFERS platform provides two key strengths. First, it encompasses all key phases of the emergency management cycle, ensuring a comprehensive management of the emergencies. Second, the system embraces a modular and service-oriented architecture, allowing each IS to operate independently with minimal dependencies. This modularity is further enhanced by asynchronous communication through a message broker, allowing for more flexibility. To further maximize interoperability, the platform leverages several software standards, including REST API communication for web-based components, INSPIRE metadata, OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium)-compliant services for GIS data management. This standardised approach allows for easier integration with existing systems and applications when necessary, fostering collaboration among various stakeholders involved in forest fire emergency management.

This work aims to provide an overview of the SAFERS ISs and platform, focusing on its architecture and technical aspects. Through this comprehensive analysis, we aim to highlight the innovative features and capabilities of the overall platform, with particular attention to the innovations brought to the domain of forest fire emergency management.

The remainder of this document is organised as follows. Section 2 will delve into the SAFERS architecture, followed by an examination of the ISs and their operational and on-demand functionalities in Section 3. Additionally, the data layer, which plays a critical role in integrating diverse data sources, will be explored in Section 4. Section 5 provides an overview of the SAFERS dashboard, which is a

user-friendly web-based interface designed to enhance decision-making and situational awareness during forest fire emergencies. Finally, Section 6 draws the final conclusions, highlighting future directions for further enhancements in this field.

The SAFERS Architecture

Fig. 1 - Overview of the SAFERS architecture. The dashboard represents the main entry point, visualising the data produced by the ISs (top pane). These ISs provide information either via REST or Async API. Geospatial data is handled by the GeoData Repository (GDR), then processed by the importer and map server for visualisation.

In the SAFERS platform, the architectural design shown in **Fig. 1** is crucial in facilitating efficient communication, data management, and visualisation of heterogeneous information.

The main functionalities of the SAFERS platform are provided by a set of services independent of one another. The IS are grouped into three main categories, namely *operational services*, *on-demand services*, and *crowdsourcing solutions*.

First, the operational services represent modules with a simpler communication paradigm: they autonomously provide periodical outputs for specific data. These include Sub-seasonal Weather Forecasts, Operational Early Warnings, In-situ Smoke and Fire Detection Systems, and the Decision Support System.

Second, on-demand services, namely the EO-based Fire Delineation, Post-fire Monitoring and On-demand Wildfire Forecast services, use instead a more complex communication mechanism: they are triggered by a specific message type named *map request*. These services act on demand, retrieving the necessary data based on user-defined parameters, and producing one or more outputs, depending on the request content. Once the results become available, the other services are notified through a message bus, allowing for the required follow-up actions to take place.

Last, SAFERS also incorporates *crowdsourcing solutions*, including a chatbot and a social media module, to gather information directly or indirectly from citizens. The chatbot enables structured geolocated and multimedia data collection, while the social module gathers and classifies real-time Twitter posts, extracting relevant emergency events and estimating their impacts.

To support efficient data management, the platform includes a data layer, which serves as a central storage system for heterogeneous data. This module adheres to INSPIRE metadata standards¹, ensuring proper organisation and accessibility of diverse datasets. When applicable, the raw data stored in the GeoData Repository (GDR) is processed by the Importer and Mapper modules. These components allow the creation and management of OGC-compliant² layers, enabling the integration and presentation of spatial data within the system.

The main communication point between the user dashboard and the services is the central backend, which facilitates the exchange of information, allowing users to interact with various platform components seamlessly. This backend ensures the smooth flow of data and requests throughout the system, while a web-based dashboard is provided to users for intuitive data visualisation. The dashboard supports the display of geospatial information through Web Map Service (WMS) and Web Map Tile Service (WMTS) layers. Additionally, it incorporates data from crowdsourcing solutions and real-time information from in-situ cameras, enabling users to gain valuable insights and make informed decisions.

The SAFERS Intelligent Services

Fig. 2 - Example outputs derived from the on-demand services: (1) wildfire forecast simulation, (2) severity estimation, (3) post-fire dNBR analysis, (4) fuel map delineation.

The ISs have the purpose to provide heterogeneous data in a timely manner to the SAFERS Dashboard. These services are carefully designed to address specific aspects of the emergency management cycle, enhancing preparedness, response, and mitigation efforts.

Operational Services. These play a critical role in providing high-quality information relevant to forest fires. Data are essential for preventing, preparing, and responding to potentially dangerous wildfire hazard weather situations. To achieve this, an automated processing chain has been established, allowing for the accessibility of necessary resources within the SAFERS platform, provisioned by four services. First, the Sub-seasonal Weather Forecasts service provides forecast data

¹ <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu>

² <https://www.ogc.org>

collected from the ECMWF³, focusing on relevant variables for forest fire hazard and risk prediction. The data includes high-resolution deterministic forecasts with hourly updates up to 72 hours, as well as medium-range probabilistic predictions for lead times up to 15 days (360 hours). Additionally, extended range/sub-seasonal probabilistic predictions with lead times up to 46 days (1104h) are provided twice a week. All weather data is post-processed, automatically uploaded to the SAFERS GeoData Repository, and made available for visualisation and sharing with other partner services.

Second, the Operational Early Warnings service augments operational wildfire hazard and risk mapping to improve the dissemination, uptake, and updating of early warnings. By integrating open datasets from complementing sources and utilising novel risk models, this service delivers valuable information to stakeholders, enabling daily assessment and preparation in case of a wildfire. The datasets used include the European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS)⁴, Fire Weather Index (FWI), European weather forecasts from FMI, and real-time information about active fires. The wildfire risk modelling module integrates current and forecast weather information, and it is expected to incorporate lightning forecasts.

Third, the Smoke and Fire Detection System (smoCAM) utilizes standard surveillance cameras to monitor large areas for wildfire and smoke, automatically detecting fire and smoke plumes in various outdoor conditions. This AI-based service is capable of accurately detecting smoke and fire, even in challenging environmental conditions such as clouds and fog. SmoCAM is deployed in 6 test sites, each equipped with a PTZ (Pan-Tilt-Zoom) camera and an LTE router to enable remote connections. The camera patrols different points of view to widen the monitored area, and relevant information describing the detected smoke and fire is transmitted as JSON messages to the SAFERS bus. The messages are then integrated and displayed on the dashboard, providing real-time updates on detected wildfire events.

Last, the Decision Support System (DSS) analyses data from various sources and provides valuable recommendations to stakeholders. It utilizes semantic reasoning on top of the SAFERS domain ontology to derive new insights from pre-existing knowledge. The DSS has been designed to meet user requirements and address specific scenarios, such as FWI forecasts, Fine Fuel Moisture, duff moisture, and drought anomalies. The system's functionalities have been implemented to accommodate for the SAFERS ontology, derived from previous works [2]. The DSS plays a crucial role in aiding decision-makers during forest fire emergencies, contributing to the resilience and effectiveness of the overall system.

On-demand services. SAFERS also offers services that can be activated on demand to provide rapid mapping, severity assessment, and wildfire forecast functionalities, as shown in **Fig. 2**. First, the EO-based delineation service leverages Sentinel-2 satellite imagery to generate thematic maps for burned area delineation [3], severity estimation, fire front detection, and land cover maps [4] through machine learning models. By employing state-of-the-art segmentation networks, this service generates output maps for a given area and time interval accurately, and in a short

³ <https://www.ecmwf.int>

⁴ <https://effis.jrc.ec.europa.eu>

amount of time. The service is deployed using a multi-module containerized architecture, ensuring fault-tolerance and distribution of components, and asynchronous communication through the SAFERS message bus.

Similarly, the Post-fire Monitoring service generates long-term assessments during the recovery period, providing dNBR and other layers to better observe and understand the regrowth in the affected areas.

The Wildfire Forecast service is instead achieved through the implementation of PROPAGATOR [5], an operational tool based on cellular automata. It rapidly simulates the potential spread of wildfires, considering various factors such as ignition point, topography, fuel cover, and meteorological data. The resulting probabilistic fire fronts stem from averaging several realizations of the stochastic core, and the service provides useful accessory data, including maximum and mean Rate of Spread (RoS) and Fireline Intensity (FI) of the affected area. The simulation also allows for the incorporation of firefighting actions, such as Canadair and helicopter drops, and waterlines. The IS is deployed with async communication using the message broker, enabling efficient orchestration of simulation requests. The results are uploaded to the data repository, and the dashboard receives timely updates from both services.

Crowdsourcing solutions. Currently, operational procedures primarily involve one-way communication from authorities and monitoring agencies to citizens, lacking active citizen engagement. This deficiency leads to inadequate risk awareness and preparedness among citizens, hindering disaster impact reduction in the case of natural hazards. Valuable information shared by citizens on social media during emergencies often gets lost in the vast sea of data. To address these challenges, SAFERS proposes implementing two essential crowdsourcing solutions: the Social Module and the Chatbot.

The Social Module is designed to fetch and analyse real-time content posted on Twitter⁵, with a particular focus on wildfires and other natural disasters. By combining text and image analysis with location information, the module utilizes natural language and image processing to extract meaningful data related to emergency situations, early warning signals, and damage assessment. A first rule-based filtering excludes erroneous or misleading data, retaining only informative content relevant to emergency scenarios. The module then classifies social media posts using text mining and deep learning techniques, mapping them into relevant categories [6], and groups them by meaningful events [7] [8]. Implemented and deployed in a cloud platform, the Social Module seamlessly integrates with the SAFERS message bus through secured web-based (HTTPS) REST APIs, ensuring efficient data sharing and enhancing the overall emergency response capabilities.

The Chatbot [8] facilitates instead structured geolocated and multimedia data collection from first responders and volunteers, serving as an innovative and user-centric tool by enhancing communication and collaboration during disaster management efforts. It enables two-way communication between citizens, field forces, and control centres, crucial for effective disaster risk reduction. Built on a robust technology stack, the Chatbot ensures scalability and seamless integration with the

⁵ <https://twitter.com/>

Telegram API, enabling efficient real-time communication and personalized functionalities for different user roles. Two primary user roles are supported: professionals with specialized training and citizens. For professionals, the chatbot offers advanced features like real-time location sharing, reporting activities, detailed measurements, damage assessments, and instructions exchange with the control room, facilitating efficient emergency coordination. Citizens, with limited emergency response training, can actively contribute by reporting events, sharing real-time information, receiving geolocated broadcast messages, and accessing safety guidelines through the Chatbot.

Both the Social Module and the Chatbot integrate with the project-level API Gateway and OAuth2⁶ authentication module to ensure secure data management and user authentication, safeguarding user accounts and associated data.

The Data Layer

Fig. 3 - Data layer components and their interaction with the other modules.

Every service introduced so far generates heterogeneous outputs that need to be stored and processed to be visualized and exploited by expert users. This is the task of the data layer, which consists of two main components: the Geodata Repository (GDR), and the Importer-Mapper coupling, displayed in **Fig. 3**.

The GDR consists of a management component that facilitates data ingestion and retrieval by serving as a central repository for metadata. It enables efficient data discovery and exploration within the data repository. This component is built on CKAN⁷, an open-source data management system that has been customized with plugins and extensions to meet the specific requirements of the GDR. CKAN provides a user-friendly web-based GUI and API for users to upload, edit, delete, and search data. The large amount of data in various formats is securely stored in a cloud big data storage system, using a data lake approach and employing the HDFS file system to preserve data in its original form within Hadoop clusters [9].

⁶ <https://oauth.net/2/>

⁷ <https://ckan.org>

To ensure effective communication and collaboration between microservices, the GDR exploits the message bus to notify other services about new data availability and changes to existing datasets.

The Importer-Mapper consists instead of two interconnected elements. The Mapper represents a map server that exposes geospatial data through OGC-compliant services, i.e., WMS, WMTS, WFS, or WCS, implemented through GeoServer⁸. The Importer routine handles changes in the raw data stored in the GeoData Repository and updates the content available through the Mapper. It can handle data in various formats, transforming and publishing it as layers. The Importer component provides additional APIs to enhance its functionality. These APIs allow users to retrieve the list of available layers, delete layers from both GeoServer and the GDR, obtain metadata for specific layers, download raw files associated with layers, and access the temporal series of values for specific coordinates from a list of layers. By supporting multiple data formats and offering standardized services, the Importer-Mapper components ensure a seamless integration and retrieval of geospatial data from different sources.

The SAFERS Dashboard

Fig. 4 - Screenshots of the SAFERS dashboard, displaying the main screen (left), and an example form to create a new map request.

The SAFERS dashboard, illustrated in **Fig. 4**, stands as a pivotal interface for managing and visualizing critical data throughout various phases of forest fire emergencies effectively. Developed on React JS framework and integrating essential libraries, this dashboard ensures a seamless and intuitive user experience. The dashboard handles the complexities of spatio-temporal data representation, with the central map serving as a geographical anchor, and the top-level date and time selectors as global temporal reference for the whole system.

The visualization methods employed within the dashboard offer multiple approaches to better understand the data. Dynamic filters in the top bar enhance data exploration, enabling users to refine their focus and select increasingly specific information. This allows for a more precise analysis, crucial in making informed

⁸ <https://geoserver.org/>

decisions during emergency situations. The central map not only provides essential geographical context but also allows users to interact directly with the data.

A user-friendly list pane on the left side offers a streamlined approach to navigation, ensuring that users can effortlessly access the necessary information. The dashboard integrates and handles OGC-compliant layers, complete with their respective legends and metadata. This feature enables users to grasp spatial relationships and patterns. Moreover, the use of INSPIRE metadata standards ensures seamless data sharing and interoperability among European stakeholders. To further enhance the temporal analysis, the inclusion of a dedicated time widget grants users the ability to explore data across different timeframes, including the map layers. Additionally, the dashboard allows retrieving data at specific points, offering the tools for the analysis on the time series, displaying the evolution of a given metric in a specific location (e.g., precipitation, temperature).

Lastly, the dashboard also provides a dedicated summary page, offering a comprehensive overview of ongoing emergency situations. This page consolidates critical information, providing stakeholders with a comprehensive snapshot, and allowing users to grasp the current situation at a glance.

Conclusions

The SAFERS project presents a comprehensive and modular forest fire management system, addressing the challenges posed by increasing forest fires and extreme weather events. The SAFERS ISs form a powerful backbone, offering essential functionalities across all emergency management phases. Operational services provide high-quality weather forecasts for early warnings and risk prediction, while on-demand services facilitate rapid mapping and severity assessment using satellite imagery. Crowdsourcing solutions actively engage citizens in data collection and real-time communication. Overall, the SAFERS platform leverages intelligent technologies like AI and EO, empowering informed decision-making and fostering resilience in forest fire emergency management, contributing to more resilient societies and mitigating future fire impacts.

Acknowledgements

This work was carried out in the context of the Horizon 2020 project SAFERS (Grant Agreement n.869353).

References

- [1] W. Knorr, L. Jiang and A. Arneth, "Climate, CO₂ and human population impacts on global wildfire emissions," *Biogeosciences*, vol. 13, p. 267–282, 2016.
- [2] C. Maltoni, C. Rossi and G. Sánchez, "Improving resilience to emergencies through advanced cyber technologies: the I-REACT project," *Geomedica*, vol. 21, 2017.
- [3] E. Arnaudo, L. Barco, M. Merlo and C. Rossi, "Robust Burned Area Delineation through Multitask Learning," in *Conference on Machine Learning and Principles and Practice of Knowledge Discovery in Databases*, 2023.
- [4] M. Galatola, E. Arnaudo, L. Barco, C. Rossi and F. Dominici, "Land Cover Segmentation with Sparse Annotations from Sentinel-2 Imagery," in *IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium (IGARSS 2023)*, 2023.
- [5] A. Trucchia, M. D'Andrea, F. Baghino, P. Fiorucci, L. Ferraris, D. Negro, A. Gollini and M. Severino, "PROPAGATOR: An operational cellular-automata based wildfire simulator," *Fire*, vol. 3, p. 26, 2020.
- [6] S. Piscitelli, E. Arnaudo and C. Rossi, "Multilingual text classification from twitter during emergencies," in *2021 IEEE International Conference on Consumer Electronics (ICCE)*, 2021.
- [7] D. Salza, E. Arnaudo, G. Blanco and C. Rossi, "A 'glocal' approach for real-time emergency event detection in twitter," in *ISCRAM 2022 Conference Proceedings-19th International Conference on Information Systems for Crisis Response and Management*, 2022.
- [8] K. Konstantoudakis, K. Christaki, D. Sainidis, I. Babic, D. G. Kogias, G. Inglese, L. Bruno, G. Giunta, C. Z. Patrikakis, O. Balet and others, "Common Operational Picture and Interconnected Tools for Disaster Response: The FASTER Toolkit," in *Disaster Management and Information Technology: Professional Response and Recovery Management in the Age of Disasters*, Springer, 2022, p. 83–110.
- [9] D. Borthakur and others, "HDFS architecture guide," *Hadoop apache project*, vol. 53, p. 2, 2008.